

Data interoperability in health surveillance: a literature review to support the development of One Health frameworks

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9 **Keywords: Public health; animal health; health surveillance; semantic interoperability; disease**
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11 **Abstract**

12 This literature review aims to investigate the state-of-art in data interoperability solutions in health
13 surveillance. Focus was given to the identification of methodologies which can support the
14 construction of a framework for One Health (OH) Surveillance. As OH relies on data reuse across
15 multiple health sectors, and preservation of the original context of the data is fundamental for correct
16 inference and decision making, particular focus was given to semantic interoperability (ensuring the
17 integrity and meaning of the data across systems). Papers were grouped and presented by the context
18 of interoperability application. Within each context, we highlighted interoperability needs and the
19 solutions reported. In all contexts presented, however, a clear narrative was repeated, with
20 approaches based on the use of data models and coding of data based on specific terminologies
21 (schema representation approaches) being replaced by knowledge modeling and ontology-based
22 solutions as systems evolved, and in particular as the complexity of the data usage context increased.
23 While challenges to implementation in practice and scalability are still present, the evidence brought
24 up by this review made it clear that it is possible to build a framework of OHS that is designed as a
25 knowledge layer capable of connecting data on demand, while preserving data sources context and
26 structure.

27 **1 Introduction**

28 One current definition of One-Health surveillance (OHS) is “the systematic collection, validation,
29 analysis, interpretation of data and dissemination of information collected on humans, animals and
30 the environment to inform decision for more effective, evidence- and system-based health
31 interventions”(1). Bordier et al, 2018 (2) pointed out that other concurrent definitions of OHS all
32 emphasize the role of cross-sectoral collaboration in the improvement of health management.

33 Barriers to data sharing are often listed when evaluating challenges to the establishment of such
34 cross-sectoral frameworks (1–3). The challenge of extracting information from data coming from
35 such heterogeneous contexts goes far beyond the simple access and aggregation of data. Ammon and
36 Makela (2010) (4) described in details the integrated collection and analysis of data on zoonoses in

37 the European Union (EU), first established in 1992, and currently a joint task of the European Centre
38 for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) and the European Food Safety Agency (EFSA). Despite
39 this opportunity for joint data analysis, the authors pointed out several challenges to data
40 comparability, from methodological differences between countries, and challenges of data quality
41 and validation, to differences of population structure and population reporting level among sectors.
42 The experience reported highlighted the complex data and meta-data structure needed to capture and
43 take into account all the contextual information needed about the data collected and the data
44 collection processes.

45 Within individual countries, activities of surveillance in public health (PH), animal health (AH) and
46 food safety (FS) all generate data which can contribute to OHS. Converting those data into valuable
47 information for decision requires not necessarily that those data are aggregated, but that they are
48 interoperable, so that sharing can be performed on demand, for specific problems, respecting various
49 models of data disclosure. Interoperability focuses on cooperation among systems, referring to their
50 ability to continuously communicate and exchange information, and *use* the information that has
51 been exchanged (5,6).

52 This literature review aimed to investigate the state-of-art in data interoperability solutions in health
53 surveillance. Focus was given to the identification of methodologies which can support the
54 construction of an OHS framework. That is, support the multidisciplinary reuse of data from multiple
55 knowledge domains in a collaborative environment, producing information for decision making
56 across all sectors involved.

57 **2 Methods**

58 The following search string was entered in Scopus on 1st of July, 2020:

59 *TITLE-ABS-KEY(data AND (((public OR population OR animal) AND health) OR*
60 *((health OR disease* OR infectio* OR zoono* OR veterinar* OR medic*) AND*
61 *(surveillance OR monitoring)) OR (outbreak* OR epidem* OR epizoot*)) AND*
62 *(interoperability))*

63 The string searches title, abstract and keywords of all published resources indexed in Scopus, to
64 match the following criteria:

- 65 1. Must have the word “data”
- 66 2. Must have the word “interoperability”
- 67 3. The health surveillance scope can be defined by:
 - 68 a. the occurrence of the expressions “public health”, “population health”, or “animal
69 health”; OR
 - 70 b. the words “surveillance” or “monitoring” in combination with any of the following
71 words: health, disease, any word with the root “infectio”(covering infection,
72 infectious, etc), any word with the root “zoono”(zoonoses, zoonotic, etc), words with
73 root “veterinar”, or words starting with “medic”.

74 We did *not* exclude conference abstracts, as we were interested in state-of-art solutions, and new
75 ideas and solutions may still not be published in full original articles. Titles and abstracts of all
76 retrieved papers were read by the two authors, who voted on inclusion or exclusion. The authors were
77 able to vote blind to each other’s vote using the freely available literature review tool Rayyan (7).

78 The following overarching inclusion criterium was used: the publication must refer to a specific data
79 interoperability solution, addressing joint analysis of data from different sources. The following
80 exclusion criteria were applied:

- 81 • Not available in English.
- 82 • Not primary research.
- 83 • Publications which refer to data interoperability in the “data format” sense, not as a challenge
84 to combining content. A particular example of this case were the many papers addressing data
85 interoperability between computers and wearable devices.
- 86 • Publications which discuss needs and demands for interoperability, not presenting any
87 particular data interoperability solution.
- 88 • Publications focused on data collection guidance (that is, standardisation of data collection,
89 rather than addressing the issue of interoperability of already existing data), data collection
90 tools or database development.
- 91 • Publications describing a specific terminology, standard or ontology, but not discussing the
92 scenario of data interoperability it aims to address.

93 Abstracts accepted by at least one reviewer were subjected to full-text review, during which the same
94 inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied focusing on exclusion criteria that were not obvious
95 from reading only the abstract.

96 **3 Results**

97 The search returned 1198 unique results, after we excluded publications duplicated or not in English.
98 After abstract screening, 324 papers were subjected to full-text review, and 135 were accepted after
99 the two rounds of screening.

100 As we read the full-texts during the screening, it became clear that there were two dimensions of
101 interoperability being discussed: structural and semantic. Structural or syntactic interoperability
102 refers to the format of data exchange (6). In the EU, the particular context within which we aimed to
103 inform the advancement of an OHS framework, EFSA and ECDC have done significant work, in
104 their respective domains, to solve the problem of *structural interoperability* among datasets from
105 different European member states (MS). These agencies gather standardised and validated data into
106 the Data Collection Framework (DCF)(8) and The European Surveillance System (TESSy)(9),
107 respectively. These standardised datasets, collating surveillance information at the European level,
108 can be accessed through different resources made available by these agencies.

109 *Semantic interoperability*, on the other hand, is concerned with ensuring the integrity and *meaning* of
110 the data across systems (6). Semantic interoperability is particularly important in OHS in order to
111 allow data reuse across sectors, and reuse of data for research and knowledge discovery, while
112 preserving the original context of the data.

113 From the 135 papers subjected to full-text review, 43 addressed only structural interoperability.
114 These papers are listed in the Supplementary Material, and will not be discussed further.

115 The 92 remaining papers were reviewed to identify and try to group the data sources used, the
116 knowledge domains involved, the nature of the interoperability problem they addressed, and the type
117 of interoperability solution adopted. None of these characteristics alone provided an easy way to

118 categorize and group all papers to present their findings, but smaller groups started emerging from
119 this classification, from which we could gather lessons.

120 Grouping papers based on their data sources, we first discuss 4 papers which addressed specifically
121 the integration of geographical data into health research.

122 A large number of papers used electronic health records (EHR) as a data source, but in different
123 contexts. The 44 that used EHR in the context of individual health care or clinical research are
124 presented first, and then the 13 which attempted to reuse knowledge for the construction of
125 population level applications, in particular surveillance applications.

126 Moving beyond the data source into system application goals, we present 10 further papers which
127 dealt with the construction of public health surveillance systems, and 14 which presented other multi-
128 domain interoperability contexts within health.

129 Lastly, we present 7 papers which bring forward semantic interoperability frameworks developed and
130 made available for use in biomedical applications – these are generic frameworks, developed to be
131 used anywhere where semantic interoperability is needed.

132 As we review the papers' contributions, we highlight needs addressed and *solutions employed*. It is
133 outside the scope of this review to provide a theoretical background for these solutions and the
134 technologies listed. Rather, we focus on the context in which they are applied. We will also not
135 address issues related to data sharing, access, or governance.

136 **3.1 Data source: geographical data (n=4)**

137 Three papers from Gao and collaborators, published over four years (10–12), give a good overview
138 of the evolution of methods and solutions for incorporating geographical information services in
139 health surveillance.

140 In the first paper, Gao et al. (2008) (12) identified four major challenges for the development of
141 health geographic applications: (i) implementation of various health mapping methods in many web-
142 based applications without proper data source description and methods declaration; (ii) need to
143 support many mapping dimensions for health data representation; (iii) constrains to integration and
144 reusability of health applications; and (iv) lack of interoperability between applications. Within the
145 interoperability problems (iv) described by the authors, there are two dimensions to differentiate: data
146 interoperability, versus system (service) interoperability. The first, of interest in this review, was
147 addressed by the authors by the development of a Health Representation Extensible Markup
148 Language (XML) *schema* for sharing of health results.

149 In a following paper (11) the authors again reflected on the challenges to develop collaborative
150 systems of disease mapping that can empower disease outbreak detection and control in a multi-
151 institutional, cross-border environment, this time adding concerns over appropriate cartographical
152 representations and sensitive dissemination of disease data as a current challenge. The authors also
153 extended the discussion on data heterogeneities to highlight the difference between semantic and
154 syntactic interoperability, already addressed here, plus the issue of “schematic heterogeneities”,
155 defined by the authors as referring to “diversity in representations or storage models”. The authors
156 suggested that all levels of heterogeneities could be overcome with proper *schema representation*
157 *approaches*. Their new proposed architecture had an additional layer responsible for data matching
158 and transformation tasks, responsible for converting data from multiple sources into a common

159 schema. The authors were able to demonstrate disease data sharing in a distributed network achieving
160 high flexibility and interoperability. As they discuss, this would make possible for health
161 organizations to generate specific disease mapping and process services, which are then added to a
162 catalogue of interoperable, similar solutions, sharing the costs of disease data collection and analysis,
163 while building the capacity for cross-border disease management. As the authors report, however, the
164 schema-based solution represents very low semantic interoperability, and the development of a
165 *standard ontology* for spatio-temporal disease data would improve the effectiveness and efficiency of
166 the architecture, empowering the construction of truly interoperable distributed disease services.

167 Following this goal, their next paper reviewed (10) was focused on a health information system
168 allowing semantic querying. Based on the premise that “with well-designed ontologies, the meaning
169 of distributed data can be unambiguously defined; semantic heterogeneity can be resolved, and
170 therefore data sharing and integration can be enabled”, the authors developed an architecture where
171 *ontologies* are used in the map/visualization tier, to allow semantic querying by the user; and also in a
172 reasoning server able to connect the various concepts needed to correctly display health data
173 geographically. Rules are defined in the reasoner to allow deducing of new information based on
174 ontologies and facts.

175 The authors also pointed out that ontologies allow enrichment of data as well as metadata, naming
176 four types of ontologies needed in this specific application: health domain ontologies, geometric
177 ontologies, topological ontologies and cartographic ontologies. For this application, a respiratory
178 disease ontology was built. While various ontologies for health exist, the authors highlight efforts to
179 map and translate between ontologies.

180 Lastly, Martins and Rocha (2012)(13) studied the feasibility of a distributed web based application to
181 support integration of data on bluetongue (an infectious disease of domestic and wild ruminants)
182 surveillance across European countries. The authors reported that “syntactical interoperability was
183 guaranteed by the use of Open Geospatial consortium standards”, and “semantic interoperability was
184 assured by design, by developing a *unique data model*”. As the full-text was not available, we don’t
185 have more information about how this common data model was enforced or implemented.

186 **3.2 Data source: EHR; applications focused on individual health care (n=44)**

187 Data integration across different systems that produce EHR, such as different clinics, was an issue
188 more often addressed only through syntactic interoperability (see Supplementary Material). If all data
189 sources belong to the same domain, and the data produced will be used in the same context (within
190 domain), the integration was mostly structural. In that context of syntactic interoperability, data
191 standards were a commonly employed solution.

192 Moving towards semantic interoperability, Hamm et al. (2007)(14) and Khan et al. (2013)(15)
193 highlighted that there is no universally accepted coding scheme, and interoperability based on
194 *standards* is restricted to data coded using the same specific terminology. Paraiso-Medina et al.
195 (2015)(16) further pointed out that data integration based on data coding is still mainly a manual task.
196 All three group of authors proposed *semantic modelling* of concepts among different clinical
197 terminologies. In the work of Hamm et al. (14) an *automated code matching process* was
198 investigated.

199 Semantic interoperability was introduced when there was a clear emphasis in data re-use. A typical
200 scenario of data re-use within health care was the information flow between various components of
201 medical information systems. Akatkin et al (2017) (17) compared semantic integration to classic

202 interaction via mediators, and the creation of *standard data models in XML*. Their conference
203 abstract concludes on the advantages of a semantic core for the creation of a digital health ecosystem
204 (but very limited information is provided in this abstract). Already in 2006, Orgun and Vu (18)
205 proposed a framework for interactions in a distributed medical systems environment. Their multi-
206 agency system relied on model based on the *Health Level Seven (HL7) message standard*, widely
207 adopted to exchange health data. This provided a semi-automatic tool to map among the various
208 distributed sources within the information system, in replacement of relying solely on manual coding
209 by human analysts. The use of a healthcare *ontology* was the solution proposed by Miller and
210 Maccaull (2009)(19) to connect the various tasks in a health care flow, from assessments, to
211 procedures, therapies, laboratory diagnostics, etc. Kiourtis et al. (2018)(20) proposed a mechanism
212 for doing that while matching ontology content to HL7 resources. Wang et al. (2013) (21) extended
213 the idea further, using the power of knowledge representation through ontologies to not only connect
214 systems and allow data to flow among them, but to create personalised clinical pathways for
215 individual patients, improving treatment quality and efficiency of healthcare organisations.

216 Rosenbloom et al. (2017)(22) and de Madariaga et al. (2014)(23) also emphasized the role of
217 semantic integration when the goal is knowledge discovery from the data available. The former
218 authors reviewed initiatives based in standardized data models to support clinical research from EHR
219 data, while the latter emphasized data re-use in a context of evolving knowledge. They proposed an
220 *explicit separation of information and knowledge*. A reference model is proposed for representation
221 of clinical data, while the knowledge that connects the concepts in the data is modelled with higher
222 degree of semantics, and can be subjected to updates.

223 When EHR was specifically reused to improve clinical research, eight papers proposed solutions
224 based on establishing *common data models or elements*, relying on the mapping of individual data
225 sources into these single models or standardized terminologies (24–31). Mohanty et al. (2008) (28)
226 demonstrated how these common data elements (CDE) can be used to construct information models.
227 A formalization of these models into *ontologies* to support cross-domain data integration and reuse in
228 clinical research was the solution described in three other clinical research papers (32–34). Rath et al.
229 (2012) (34) presented the evolution of Orphanet, a multilingual information portal for rare diseases,
230 and stated that the need for an ontology grew from the increasing complexity of the knowledge base
231 in terms of maintenance, quality control, and interoperability needs. Antoniadis et al. (2017) (33)
232 presented Linked2Safety, an ontology based solution for knowledge discovery over multiple,
233 distributed EHR sources, while keeping their anonymization and security. In this approach, data are
234 aggregated into *data cubes*, which are then semantically annotated with a reference ontology.

235 The remaining papers promoting semantic interoperability among EHR data sources, with the
236 specific goal of improving clinical decision support, all implemented solutions based on the use of
237 *ontologies and knowledge modelling*. These were 10 papers discussing the general integration of
238 EHR data sources and their reuse to build models for clinical decision or knowledge discovery (35–
239 44); and 12 papers addressing clinical research in a very specific context (such as child obesity or
240 brain imaging) or even specific diseases (45–56). Among the latter, the work of Li et al. (2020) (56)
241 was published early during the COVID-19 pandemic, proposing clinical guidelines for the disease
242 using an openEHR template. OpenEHR are a set of community maintained programmes to support
243 open specifications of clinical models in health care, allowing explicit modeling of the domain
244 knowledge separated from the data representation (57). As Li et al. (56) noted, the fast evolving
245 knowledge about the disease demanded the use of frameworks that supported semantic explicit and
246 collaborative modeling to meet the dynamic data requirements during the global crisis.

247 These papers notably emphasized the adoption of solutions that do not require data to be aggregated
248 – rather, they take into account the increasingly distributed nature of the data sources, and the
249 impossibility of attempting to aggregate all data into a single database or server. Connectivity and
250 interoperability are implemented in this *federated architecture* through the use of smart clients,
251 capable of placing queries over the distributed data sources. As ontologies can be constructed to be
252 interoperable among themselves, there is potential to build large knowledge graphs that connect
253 models from various domains and contexts, and can then be applied to networks of distributed data.
254 When it comes to realizing this potential in practice with currently available technology, however,
255 authors identify challenges related both to the availability of tools that can be easily integrated into
256 workflows used by medical experts, as well as the capacity to reason over large amounts of data.
257 Regarding the latter, in particular, Barisevičius et al. (2018) (58) joined many publicly available
258 ontologies of biomedical relevance into one *Linked Data Graph* (LDG), attempting to use the
259 resulting model to empower a chatbot in the medical app Babylon. The authors cautioned against the
260 rapid growing complexity of the model, and concluded with a decision to redo their LDG from
261 scratch, using a more conservative and parsimonious approach.

262 **3.3 Data source: EHR; applications focused on population health (n=13)**

263 In a series of three papers (59–61), Lopez and Blobel described a business and information
264 architecture for the specification of a national system in Colombia that provided semantic integration
265 between public health surveillance and clinical information systems. In the system proposed by the
266 authors, normalization was ensured by adopting the Unified Modeling Language (UML) a *standard*
267 *language* to express the information. UML is widely used in clinical systems and was mentioned in a
268 large number of the EHR papers reviewed above. The authors discussed the need for balance
269 between languages that allow for domain knowledge modeling with participation of domain experts,
270 such as UML, and more formal models, which allow more strict semantic control by expressing
271 programmatically additional constraints that are normally expressed in UML diagrams in natural
272 language. An approach suggested by the authors to achieve such balance is the harmonization of
273 UML diagrams using domain reference models, terminologies and vocabulary. The idea was
274 developed in (61), where the authors focused more on the semantic interoperability issues of the
275 system developed, and presented the construction of *UML profiles*. These profiles are UML packages
276 containing the model that allows repurposing of clinical data for the public health information
277 system, and are exchanged between tools using XML metadata interchange (XMI).

278 The creation of a “*public health profile*” within the systems already in place for exchange of
279 individual health records was also the approach suggested by Renly et al. (2009) (62). Syntactic and
280 semantic interoperability were addressed by enforcing the use of a *common vocabulary* (SNOMED-
281 CT), but a specific profile was created with the agreed information that should be reported in cases of
282 laboratorial confirmation of foodborne pathogens. Population level utility was further created by
283 allowed queries that were not patient centric, that is, queries where the patient field was left empty.
284 Khalique and Khan (2019)(63) developed a framework that could be installed in participating
285 hospitals to *map* their EHR data into a public health record model, and transmit this information
286 further for use at the population level.

287 Two abstracts described an initiative to improve surveillance at the national level in Namibia by
288 connecting hospital systems with the specific purpose of sharing and exchanging disease-surveillance
289 information (64,65), but details about the interoperability solutions used were not available.

290 The CrowdHEALTH project (66) aimed to “introduce a new paradigm of Holistic Health Records
291 (HHR)”, and proposed a platform to augment EHR records with other sources of information that
292 allow building knowledge on health determinants. In the proposed structure, the authors point to an
293 “Interoperability Layer”, where they describe that “data are aggregated into HHR through different
294 data models and query languages”. More details about this part of the system were not the focus of
295 the publication found.

296 An *ontology-based* approach to integrate data from different health care providers, and even
297 incorporate data from air pollution to enable research on this as a risk factor for stroke over time, was
298 adopted in (67). The authors describe a four-step data transformation approach in which data and
299 metadata are mapped into *Web Ontology Language (OWL)* formats, resulting into an integrated, and
300 semantically queryable set of files.

301 As an alternative to building systems that integrate or allow notification of data from individuals to a
302 central public health information system, the *federated query approach* sees the existing clinical
303 systems as repositories that could respond to a central query. The “Query Health” system (68)
304 sought to develop a workflow that allowed investigators to compose queries, securely distribute the
305 question through a network of data repositories, and combine the aggregated results. Of particular
306 importance in this review was their pilot application of population-based surveillance using EHR
307 data. Query composition and processing were implemented as a graphical, web-based query builder
308 using the Informatics for Integrating Biology and the Bedside (i2b2) platform. I2b2 provides a set of
309 web-services components (cells). An ontology cell was used to enable translation and data elements
310 integration using the Query Health data *ontology*.

311 The i2b2 platform was also used by Klann and colleagues (69) to create a multi-sourced medication
312 information platform for postmarketing drug surveillance. This was not simply an exercise of
313 translation or mapping between different standards or terminologies. As the authors discuss,
314 converting medication dispensing data from a HL7v2 (HL7 reference information model, version 2)
315 to the C-CDA (Consolidated Clinical Document Architecture) format used in the EHR required data
316 conversion from a record-level based to a document based format. For input into i2b2, the data were
317 then denormalized into the Patient Data Object (PDO) format, observation-centric. For these data
318 conversions, the authors used the Model Driven Message Interoperability (MDMI) toolkit, a
319 *graphical data-mapping tool* developed with the goal of enabling health data conversion between any
320 types of data format. The tool however had to be adapted to enable a “linked data” functionality that
321 would preserve the linking between sibling records used in HL7v2, relevant for the semantic
322 meaning of records; and to be able to “flatten” the complex hierarchical structures of C-CDA into the
323 PDO structure. To enable querying of the rich database resulting from all these integration efforts,
324 querying through the i2b2 web tool is supported by *ontology hierarchies*.

325 Yuksel and colleagues (70) also built a tool for pharmacovigilance, using an *ontological framework*
326 to support both syntactic and semantic interoperability when reusing EHR data to generate
327 information for surveillance at the population level. The authors argue that the main shortcoming of
328 initiatives that address interoperability using defined terminologies/schema is that “dynamic
329 eligibility criteria execution on top of the actual data sources is not supported”. In contrast, the
330 authors propose an ontological framework that defines both the structural mapping and the semantic
331 modeling of the original data into the representations used for surveillance. This allows local systems
332 to continue using their terminology systems, while providing a translation tool that is “future-proof”
333 – eligibility criteria for the pharmacovigilance system can be evolved. Development of the
334 framework still required significant work to map terminologies in use in the data sources to a

335 common information model ontology. Moreover, it is important to note the challenges reported by
336 the authors to implement a reasoning engine able to perform in reasonable time. This imposed a
337 constraint in the reasoning requirements. A similar framework was used in (71), this time reusing
338 EHR records for the surveillance of Healthcare-Associated Infections (HAI), and supported by the
339 HAI ontology (HAIO). The authors used an upper level ontology (SemanticsScience Integrated
340 Ontology – SIO) for “consistent knowledge representation across physical, processual and
341 information entities”, and aligned with the Extra Simple Time Ontology (ESTO) to support temporal
342 knowledge management.

343 **3.4 Interoperability in public health surveillance (n=10)**

344 Pandiyan et al. (2011) (72) proposed an interoperable “Infectious Diseases Reporting System”, which
345 would improve efficiency and reduce timeliness in tracking and identifying epidemic outbreaks and
346 emerging infectious diseases by connecting disease reporters (clinics and hospitals) directly to a
347 centralized repository accessible by regulatory agencies. To solve the challenges posed by the
348 diversity of software structures and data standardization practices (or lack of) among the healthcare
349 providers, the authors suggested a semantic layer responsible for retrieval and mapping of the
350 information into a unified standard. The solution described by the authors used *Web services as a*
351 *core component for information exchange*, and the full system architecture can be found in the
352 original publication. The semantic information integration function, of relevance in this review, was
353 made possible using *ontology-based rules*. A central ontology was designed for the system, and
354 expressed in OWL. Besides providing semantic interoperability among various data sources, the
355 ontology also adds a layer of expressiveness – when a patient is diagnosed with an infectious disease
356 in the source healthcare provider, the clinical system launches the Web service that will send data to
357 the centralized system, and the ontology identifies the disease diagnosed and determines the level of
358 “criticality” of the case. Rao et al. (2014)(73) also proposed creating tools to enable reporting of
359 notifiable diseases directly from digital systems used to manage clinical information using a central
360 ontology as the interoperability solution – they developed the Public Health Ontology.

361 In the only system found for animal diseases reporting, Thaler et al. (2015)(74) also suggests the use
362 of an *ontology-based semantic layer of integration* to connect various organizations collaborating to
363 control outbreaks of exotic animal diseases.

364 Focusing not on how regulatory agencies gather health and disease information from scattered
365 sources, but on what they do with that information at the population level, Turbelin and Boëlle
366 (75,76) pointed out a lack of adoption of the open data principles, when compared for instance to
367 research data. They proposed a model to expose aggregated, summarized indicators of population
368 health, allowing these data to be available for reuse. The authors propose not a data sharing or data
369 integration model, but the adoption of practices to annotate data with interoperable formats, allowing
370 third parties (including for instance artificial intelligence-based applications for disease monitoring)
371 to access the data irrespective of their own data/system structures. The authors reviewed several non-
372 proprietary *data exchange standards*, deciding to pilot implementation of two of them: The Open
373 Data Protocol (OData)(77) and the Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange – Health Domain
374 (SDMX-HD) (78). The authors disregarded the HL7, for instance, due to its focus on patient data.
375 The original articles by the authors provide a detailed description of each implementation piloted, as
376 well as evaluations from the perspective of both the agency exposing the data and the end-user of the
377 system. The main difference pointed out by the authors, is that SDMX-HD is developed by domain
378 experts, and encourages harmonization. Expressivity relies on the use of a controlled terminology.
379 OData, arising from computer scientists, aims to be a generic application programming interface

380 (API). While this meant that extra effort was needed to create a representation for the public health
381 data being exposed, this option offered greater extensibility, generalizability and sustainability. The
382 authors also reported that OData made no formal difference between data and metadata, but the
383 authors complemented that both standards allowed annotation of metadata specifying the processing
384 from raw data to surveillance indicators. A big advantage of the more general OData framework was
385 the greater availability of end-user tools. As the authors reported, “SDMX-HD was designed
386 primarily for exchange between institutional information systems”, while OData was designed for the
387 exact type of applications the authors conceived, where data owners expose their data, and third
388 parties and applications can crawl a number of federated sources, made interoperable not just
389 syntactically through data terminologies, but semantically through knowledge models.

390 The use of OData was not reported in any other paper reviewed, but the use of *knowledge models* was
391 commonly highlighted to allow semantic interoperability when integrating multiple data sources,
392 enable extensive exploration of the integrated data, and empower knowledge discovery. Turbelin and
393 Boëlle pointed out that not all the contextual information needed to calculate and interpret population
394 health indicators comes from the raw data of cases. Population baselines/denominators are also
395 needed. Shaban-Nejad et al. (2017) (79) further pointed out that transparency and interoperability
396 further depend on documenting the algorithms and baselines used to calculate the indicators. As these
397 authors agree, the reuse of transformed (aggregated) data relies on proper documentation of not only
398 the data itself, but the processes of transformation used (data and metadata annotation). Associating
399 this information to raw data of individually reported diseases cases is not trivial, and graphical data
400 representations seem to have more and more become the tool of choice as systems got more complex.
401 In particular, *OWL expressed ontologies*.

402 Shaban-Nejad et al. (2017) (79) presented PopHR, “a knowledge-based platform to support
403 integration, analysis, and visualization of population health data”. The architecture presented by the
404 authors relies on ontologies to “collect, normalize, align, integrate, and transform both structured and
405 unstructured data from multiple sources into a consistent framework needed for large-scale analysis
406 of population health data”. The authors introduced the concept of evidence-based public health, and
407 described the expression of a model to capture causal knowledge, explicitly linking different
408 population health indicators to determinants-of-health. The use of ontology-based reasoning allowed
409 data integration and supported knowledge discovery from these data in a flexible and adaptable way.
410 The authors did point a problem with scalability. The authors stressed the need to reuse existing
411 ontologies as much as possible, as it is not feasible for a single system to keep up with the ever
412 growing volume and complexity of incoming data.

413 Al Manir et al. (2018) and Brenas et al. (2017, 2018)(80–82) described a fully implemented system
414 to provide interoperability among data from disparate sources, providing a consistent knowledge
415 source to support (dynamic) malaria surveillance. The authors listed the common challenges of
416 integrating data from multiple data sources, such as sources being scattered, the diversity of access
417 methodologies to the different data sources, and the absence of rich metadata. But more importantly,
418 they pointed out that the target itself – using these data to support decision making – is constantly
419 changing, as our knowledge about the disease and its occurrence in different regions evolve.
420 Moreover, the data sources themselves are constantly evolving, and an integration structure must be
421 capable of reacting to updates, and even adapting the underlying interoperability model to these
422 changes. The “*Semantic Interoperability and Evolution for Malaria Analytics*” (*SIEMA*) framework
423 presented by the authors allows situational monitoring by providing uninterrupted dynamic
424 surveillance queries of multiple resources. Rather than aggregating data centrally, these resources are
425 queried in the *federated model*. *Domain ontologies* are used to align, merge and integrate various

426 models that contribute knowledge for malaria control. SADI Web services ensure discoverability and
427 interoperability for resources that retrieve and transform data. Additional architecture components are
428 responsible for monitoring changes in the linked resources. As both the data and the knowledge about
429 interpreting the data changes over the time, the authors highlight that the reliability of the system is
430 highly dependent on the interoperability components, and the ability to detect and identify changes
431 that the system needs to adapt to.

432 An ontological framework to empower malaria surveillance was also developed in India (83). As in
433 the example above, the authors highlighted the number of knowledge domains involved in
434 surveillance against this vector-borne disease, the number of information generation activities that
435 need to be brought together, and the need to use a knowledge model to support integration and
436 reasoning. The authors highlighted, moreover, the capability of *ontologies* not only as an
437 interoperability tool, but also as a knowledge building instrument, capable of providing feedback
438 loops through which the surveillance system and the ontology learn and evolve.

439 **3.5 Other multi-domain contexts in health (n=14)**

440 A set of papers were related to applications within the cancer biomedical informatics grid (caBIG), a
441 “federated program of biomedical information system and tool development” spanning multiple
442 research domains (84). Within this grid, syntactic and semantic interoperability among biomedical
443 information services is provided by the cancer common ontologic representation environment
444 (caCORE). To enter the grid, a system needs to serve, through a documented API, data objects
445 derived from a domain object model that has been expressed as a UML class diagram. Phillips et al.
446 (2006) (84) described the development of the caCORE software development kit (SDK), which
447 provides a workflow to standardize and expedite UML-based modeling, development and
448 deployment of caCORE compliant systems. Vergara-Niedermayr et al. (2013)(85) highlighted that
449 most of the data sources that can enrich the grid are in relational or XML databases. They presented a
450 framework based on *model driven architecture (MDA)*, *common data elements and controlled*
451 *vocabularies* to encapsulate XML databases. The framework then exposes the backend XML
452 database as an object-oriented (UML-based) semantically annotated information model that can
453 become a potential grid endpoint. Krikov et al. (2011)(86) addressed the issue of legacy
454 compatibility, and the need to migrate existing analytical tools into the integrated grid environment.
455 They were able to achieve semantic integration of GeneHunter (a genetic epidemiology tool) with the
456 caBIG grid also using UML modeling, and the developed model was made publicly available. In
457 2012, González-Beltrán et al. (87) argued that the querying functionality of the caBIG grid, given at
458 the structural metadata level, was under-utilising the ontology-based annotations, and presented a
459 theoretical foundation for ontology-based queries over the grid’s data. The proposed framework
460 brings the power of *Semantic Web tools*, and *the linked data approach* to the grid by adding a
461 *semantic layer expressed using OWL*. While the approach depends on establishing mapping between
462 the component data schemas to a common schema, the use of OWL-based ontologies, in contracts to
463 common data elements and data models based integration, allows, as highlighted by the authors, to
464 incorporate domain knowledge into the system and make them semantically-queryable. The authors
465 highlighted this as a necessary step to allow the development of systems that need to discover
466 knowledge over datasets from different domains.

467 The challenges to the identification of patterns and knowledge discovery posed by the heterogeneity
468 of systems and distributed nature of data were brought up in the DebugIT project (Detecting and
469 Eliminating Bacteria Using Information Technology) in the specific context of the fight against
470 antibiotic resistance. The project highlighted that case-based knowledge analysis, over a large

471 amount of cases, would allow the discovery of patterns to guide alignment of antibiotics treatment
472 schemes, and in a series of papers (88–90) described the structure developed to allow data miners to
473 “query distributed clinical information systems in a semantically rich and content driven manner”
474 (88). The system requirements were identified as: providing aggregated information from numerous
475 national sources; no central data storage; providing information online, improving the current
476 timeline of supranational monitoring systems which only provide information in yearly batches; a
477 formal, semantic-aware data model; high performance; and reliable results. To fulfil these desiderata,
478 *Semantic Web technologies* were used to create an architecture where local laboratory databases
479 become semantically aware end points. Data definition ontologies (DDO) are used in each individual
480 location to provide syntactic normalization with the local information system. These are then mapped
481 to a central application ontology, the DebugIT Core Ontology (DCO). In a “view layer” this domain
482 ontology is used to provide the user with query templates to represent antimicrobial resistance
483 clinical questions. A semantic mediator coordinates the access to the different end points, translating
484 the query templates to allow local data aggregation operations. Datasets are therefore loosely coupled
485 in a federated designed, allowing on-demand querying of information to monitor antimicrobial
486 resistance evolution, without any central storage of data. The use of semantically aware models
487 allows the system to be linked to external Web resources, or other clinical research projects, and
488 makes it trivial to expand the coverage of concepts or adapt to new EHR or laboratory information
489 systems (89).

490 An architecture of federated data sources, united semantically to provide context-aware knowledge
491 discovery using a *central domain ontology*, was used to enable multiscale querying of brain data
492 (91); to develop the Parasite Knowledge Base (92); and to develop the semantic proteomics
493 dashboard (93). A central ontology to provide “an abstraction layer over siloed data” was also used to
494 create a Linked Data-based information system to track vaccines, and allow logistic planning and
495 integration with health information systems (94).

496 The federation model to create knowledge bases in health care was demonstrated in two examples
497 using different technological approaches based on resources of the *Semantic Web* (95). One example
498 was designed for users wanting to browse broadly over a number of interconnected data sources, and
499 the other for querying distributed databases with a specific focus. In both cases, a user interface
500 allows querying by users not familiar with SPARQL (the protocol and query language used in the
501 Semantic Web to retrieve and manipulate data stored in Resource Description Framework (RDF)
502 format). The examples developed by the authors were specifically focused on neuroscience, but the
503 goal of the work was to demonstrate how Semantic Web can allow the development of global life
504 science models, and point out advantages and challenges that can guide future research and tool
505 development. Data sources not already available in RDF were converted and explicitly annotated
506 using Open Biomedical Ontologies. The authors developed a social tagging tool – *aTags*. The tool
507 suggests terms from DBpedia and other domain ontologies, and users can tag relevant content
508 directly from the browser, generating a XHTML+RDFa output that can be embedded anywhere on
509 the web such as blogs, wikis, emails, or, as in the focus of this work, biomedical databases. Other
510 social tagging tools were cited.

511 The use of semantic annotation to improve machine usability and interoperability of data already
512 made publicly available was brought up by Natsiavas et al. (2018) (96) in the context of
513 pharmacovigilance. Differently from the EHR-based pharmacovigilance discussed previously, the
514 authors created a *central ontology* suggested to be used to annotate – and integrate – publicly
515 available adverse drug reaction reports. Tilahun et al. (2014) (97) suggested the same approach for
516 health data published regularly by the World Health Organization (WHO). The authors developed a

517 Linked-Open-Data (LOD) based health information representation joining over 20,000 HIV-related
518 data elements from the WHO global health observatory database with elements from DBpedia,
519 Bio2RDF and LinkedCT. The linked data are represented in RDF, integrated into a triple store, and
520 users can interact with the entire knowledge base created through a SPARQL query interface. To
521 convert the publicly available data into RDF, the authors used an Excel to RDF converter, and
522 expressed the data using the Data Cube vocabulary, a vocabulary that allows representation of
523 statistical data and associated meta-data such as space and time dimensions of the observations.

524 **3.6 Semantic interoperability frameworks for biomedical applications (n=7)**

525 Gessler et al. (2009)(98) pointed three main technology constraints to integration of systems over the
526 web, common in distributed service systems: mutability of traditional interfaces; rigidity and fragility
527 of schemas based on subsumption hierarchies; and confusions between data content and data
528 structure which can “bury” data deep in XML hierarchical structures. The authors postulated that the
529 need to have semantically explicit frameworks is driven not only by the increasing sophistication of
530 science, but also by the need to address technology limitations; and defined the three basic
531 requirements of a semantic web services architecture: common syntax, shared semantic, and semantic
532 discovery. Recognizing, however, the immense value of knowledge already accumulated in legacy
533 systems, and limitations of the Semantic Web frameworks OWL based, the authors developed a
534 hybrid framework - SSWAP (Simple Semantic Web Architecture and Protocol).

535 The authors redefined the problem of integration from “specifying a syntax and messaging layer used
536 to connect clients and providers”, into the need to “provide clients and providers a way to describe
537 their queries and data, find each other on the web, and engage semantic negotiation to determine
538 suitability-for-purpose at transaction time”. This redefined problem has three main actors – data
539 providers, data clients, and a discovery server to connect them – and in the SSWAP framework these
540 actors use ontologies to communicate in a semantically consistent manner. No central ontology is
541 enforced, and a web of ontologies grows as more resources are annotated with specific
542 domain/application ontologies. The authors envisage that this opens space for a shared evolution
543 driven by the domain communities.

544 Any provider can describe their resources using a Resource Description Graph (RDG), which is an
545 OWL document available publicly via Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP). As the framework
546 allows encapsulation of the data in any database into this graph for data transport, “[t]his leaves the
547 manipulation of the data’s “raw value” to any particular technology of the day, allowing the system
548 to evolve as new technologies are developed”(98). The authors demonstrated the practical
549 implementation of the framework by using it to semantically describe three major information
550 biomedical resources (99).

551 While the use of federated, semantically aware data networks has increasingly allowed the querying
552 of data over multiple data sources, and enabled knowledge discovery, Wilkinson et al. (2010)(100)
553 pointed out that the power of Description Logic Reasoners to generate and test hypothesis cannot be
554 leveraged in these networks when they are only able to compute inferences for a single, locally stored
555 dataset. While ontologies and Web Service Workflows are becoming increasingly used to document
556 “explicit, shareable, referenceable representations of how an experiment was done”, the authors
557 argued that these technologies had not aided “the aspects of the scientific method relating to explicit
558 discourse, disagreement, and hypothesis generation”. To allow the semi- or fully-automatic discovery
559 and pipelining of Semantic Web Services in response to *ad hoc* user queries, the authors introduced a
560 Semantic Web Service Framework composed of two main reusable components – the Semantic

561 Automated Discovery and Integration (SADI) and the Semantic Health and Research Environment
562 (SHARE) (100,101). SADI provides a set of “best-practices” for modeling Semantic Web Services in
563 the scientific domain, and the authors describe SADI-compliant tools available from both client and
564 service-provider perspectives, such as modules in Perl, Java, and a Protégé Plug-in. SHARE
565 “augments OWL reasoners with the ability to retrieve entities from remote data sources at the time of
566 reasoning” (100). Chepelev and Dumontier (2011)(102) applied the SADI/SHARE framework to
567 create a network of chemistry resources, creating a workflows of reproducible and interoperable
568 computational analyses of the exposed resources.

569 Postulating that despite awareness of their benefits, adoption of semantic web tools in life sciences
570 had been slow due mainly to barriers of adoption, Lopes and Oliveira (2011, 2012)(103,104)
571 introduced a software stack called COEUS. This “semantic web in a box”, as the authors described,
572 is meant to provide agile transition from primitive to semantically enhanced systems. COEUS
573 internal structure is based on an ontology model, which can be complemented with any external
574 ontology. COEUS is built to generate new information systems from scratch, simplifying the
575 translation process from existing formats, such as comma separated values (CSV) CSV, XML or
576 Structured Query Language (SQL), allowing these formats to be integrated with SPARQL query
577 results. The loaded content can be matched against any chosen ontology in real time. To provide
578 outward interoperability, COEUS provides an external API comprised of three layers: REST
579 (Representational state transfer) services, a SPARQL endpoint and LinkedData views. Data can be
580 requested in different formats.

581 **4 Discussion**

582 We have conducted a literature review of data interoperability solutions applied to health data
583 focusing specifically on cases where semantic interoperability was addressed. In the results section
584 we have listed the interoperability needs and solutions described in the papers included in the review.

585 A large part of the selected papers referred to work addressing the reuse of EHR, which are arguably
586 the largest source of data in the health context. Interoperability needs within the health-care system,
587 however, are dominated by the demand for system interoperability, and actual data interoperability
588 needs are mainly syntactic if data are not going to be used outside the clinical context. The search
589 string used was purposely designed to focus on health applications at the population level in general,
590 and health surveillance in particular, but a lack of focus on surveillance was not included in the
591 exclusion criteria. From the 57 articles reviewed which presented applications based on EHR, 13
592 were indeed focused on population level applications. The other 44 were included because they
593 specifically addressed semantic interoperability.

594 Semantic interoperability is a necessary condition for data re-use outside its primary context of
595 collection, integration of data from different domains, and knowledge discovery. These are all
596 necessary conditions for the development of a framework of One-health surveillance.

597 A deliberate choice was made to group and present papers not by the type of methodological
598 approach used, but by the context of application. In all contexts presented, however, a clear narrative
599 was repeated, with approaches based on the use of data models and coding of data based on specific
600 terminologies (schema representation approaches) being replaced by knowledge modeling and
601 ontology-based solutions as systems evolved, and in particular as the complexity of the data usage
602 context increased.

603 Schema-based solutions included extensive use of UML and HL7 in the health-care context, and
604 various XML-based terminologies in population health. These tools were mainly used in
605 architectures that relied on transferring of data to a central database. The increase in data volume,
606 velocity and variety created the demand for solutions that can be applied over distributed data
607 sources, without requiring these source data to be recoded or transferred. Federated architectures
608 became more common, with OWL expressed ontologies being used as a “knowledge layer” able to
609 connect, query and even reason across the disparate data sources connected by the architecture. In
610 this model, data owners increasingly make their data available through HTTP services or SPARQL
611 endpoints, rather than transferring data.

612 In this model of integration, as Gessler et al. (2009) (98) stated, data providers and data users are not
613 directly connected by a messaging layer. Instead, a semantic-explicit model is used by data providers
614 to describe their data, and for applications to define their queries. A “discovery server” is used to
615 connect these two ends, and establish fit-for-purpose “transactions” on demand. All the general
616 semantic interoperability frameworks reviewed work in this model, and OWL expressed ontologies
617 were the language used for semantically consistent communication between the actors.

618 The advantages of semantic explicit, ontology-based approaches were highlighted in every step of the
619 data to information continuum. Data owners can use data collection and storage practices that best fit
620 their purpose without compromising interoperability with other systems. Moreover, there is no
621 imposing of specific data models or coding practices that could impose a significant amount of
622 manual coding (16), or compromise legacy compatibility.

623 Data analysis and processing in this new model is not focused on gathering and cleaning data, but in
624 passing data through an information flow. Miller and Maccaull (2009) and Wang et al. (2013) (19,21)
625 demonstrated the creation of information flows at the individual care level. At the population level,
626 Shaban-Nejad et al. (2017)(79) demonstrated how the information flow can gather data from external
627 sources that allow monitoring of population health indicators and risk factors, augmenting the
628 information contained in clinical data. Klann et al. (2015) (69) also highlighted that when data are
629 reused in a new context, tools for mapping data are not enough. The process may require
630 transforming, aggregating and/or denormalizing data. Authors pointed out that the data analysis
631 process itself can be modelled and documented through the use of ontologies. Any assumption and
632 analysis choices made when aggregating data or building population health indicators, for instance,
633 can be explicitly annotated and linked to the data.

634 As Gao et al. (2012) (10) and Turbelin and Boëlle (2013)(76,105) pointed out, the use of semantic
635 explicit models allows enrichment also of metadata. This is particularly important when data needs to
636 be integrated over multiple domains, so that the context in which the data were captured can be
637 explicitly documented and taken into consideration when used for inference.

638 On the last step of the continuum, presenting information to users, various authors reported the
639 construction of graphical semantic querying interfaces. Cheung et al. (2009)(106) presented even the
640 use of social tagging to semantic explicitly annotate even data delivered as narrative texts.

641 What is continued being highlighted through these examples is the separation of data from
642 knowledge enabled by semantic modeling. Several authors (22,23,56,70,80–82) pointed out that this
643 is needed to create future-proof applications. As knowledge itself evolves, knowledge models can be
644 updated without imposing change in the structure of source data. Any data classification, aggregation
645 and filtering needed is performed on demand, keeping up to dynamic data requirements.

646 Besides promoting data interoperability, ontologies are themselves interoperable tools, and efforts
647 into knowledge modeling become cooperative. As modeling the knowledge in any domain is a
648 daunting task, especially in a scenario of ever evolving knowledge, this is another feature that
649 promotes sustainability of this approach.

650 The evidence brought up by this review makes it clear that it is possible to build a framework of OHS
651 that is designed as a knowledge layer capable of connecting data on demand, while preserving data
652 sources context and structure. But it also highlighted that realizing this potential in practice would
653 come with great challenges. Set aside the data access and governance issues that will not be discussed
654 in this review, many of the applications reviewed were research projects, and evidence of
655 implementation in practice is still scarce. There is a lack of tools that can be readily adopted by
656 domain experts, and scalability of semantic tools was a documented limitation (58,70).

657 **5 Conclusions**

658 OHS relies on the reuse of data from different domains – animal health, public health, food safety, as
659 well as environmental data and indicators of risk and health. This review showed that this can be
660 achieved by explicitly modelling the knowledge needed to integrate disparate data sources under
661 specific context questions. If modelled using ontologies, this would allow this daunting task to be
662 performed collaboratively and reusing knowledge already coded in biomedical ontologies. This will
663 further allow OHS to continue evolving, as our own understand of what “One-Health” means
664 evolves. More importantly, it would prevent One-Health to becomes just one more silo of
665 information into which we transform and transfer data.

666 **6 Abbreviations**

667 AH - animal health
668 API - application programming interface
669 C-CDA - Consolidated Clinical Document Architecture
670 CDE - common data elements
671 CSV - comma separated values
672 ECDC - European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
673 EFSA - European Food Safety Agency
674 EHR - Electronic Health Records
675 EU - European Union
676 FS - food safety
677 HL7 - Health Level Seven (HL7) message standard
678 HTTP - Hypertext Transfer Protocol
679 LDG - Linked Data Graph
680 LOD - Linked-Open-Data
681 MDA - model driven architecture
682 MS - member states (in the European Union)
683 OGC - Open Geospatial consortium
684 OHS - One-Health Surveillance
685 OWL - Web Ontology Language
686 PDO - Patient Data Object
687 PH - public health
688 RDF - Resource Description Framework
689 REST - Representational state transfer

690 SDMX-HD - Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange – Health Domain
691 SPARQL - SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
692 UML - Unified Modeling Language
693 WHO - World Health Organization
694 XML - Extensible Markup Language

695 **7 Conflict of Interest**

696 *The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial*
697 *relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.*

698 **8 Author Contributions**

699 Both authors acted as reviewers in all stages of the literature review. FCD wrote the first draft and
700 both authors reviewed the final text.

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